

THE STRATEGIES OF APPLYING ACTIVE LEARNING TO THE STUDY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation This article is devoted to the study is to reveal the specifics of the target, content, and control and evaluation components of professionally oriented teaching of students of medical specialties in English, which is significant in terms of a competency-based approach. Research tasks were solved in the process study of psychological, pedagogical, scientific, methodological and special literature; analysis and generalization of the experience of educational work.

Key words: Educational standards, cognitive activity, methodology, proactively, effectively, independently, discussing

Annotatsiya Ushbu maqola tibbiyot mutaxassisliklari talabalarini ingliz – tilini o‘qitishda kasbiy yo‘naltirilgan o‘qitishning maqsadli, mazmuni va nazorat-baholash tarkibiy qismlarining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, bu kompetentsiyaga asoslangan yondashuv nuqtai nazaridan muhimdir. Tadqiqotning vazifalari psixologik, pedagogik, ilmiy, uslubiy va maxsus adabiyotlarni o‘rganish jarayonida hal qilindi; tarbiyaviy ish tajribasini tahlil qilish va umumlashtirish.

Tayanch so‘zlar: ta‘lim standartlari, kognitiv faoliyat, metodologiya, faol, samarali, mustaqil, muhokama.

Аннотация Данная статья посвящена изучению специфики целевого, содержательного и контрольно-оценочного компонентов профессионально-ориентированного обучения студентов медицинских специальностей иностранному языку, что является значимым с точки зрения компетентностного подхода. Задачи исследования решались в процессе

изучения психолого-педагогической, научной, методической и специальной литературы; анализ и обобщение опыта воспитательной работы.

Ключевые слова: образовательные стандарты, познавательная деятельность, методика, активно, эффективно, самостоятельно, обсуждения

To several generations of schoolteachers it is well known that the tasks of activating the student's cognitive activity form the basis of both modern pedagogical theories and those used in technology practice. However, only recently, with the introduction of new educational standards, did AMO acquire a well-deserved status, moving from the category "DESIRABLE" in the "MANDATORY" category. The active nature of new educational standards ensures (with correct and conscientious approach) greater efficiency of the educational process due to the formation of an active responsible position of each student. Effective learning involves students developing a sense of success and control over learning process. Examples of this type of work include reading, listening, and thinking, which are generally referred to as individual activities. Additionally, students should plan their work, discuss their ideas, and correct each other's work in pairs, small groups, and cooperative student projects, where the choice strategies are largely dependent on tasks and deadlines. Of course, the activation of a student's cognitive activity without the development his cognitive interest is practically impossible. That's why in the process learning, we need to effectively stimulate, develop cognitive interest in students as a persistent personality trait, as an important motive for learning and as a powerful means of improving its quality. How to help a student realize his individuality and form a personality during training, teach him proactively, effectively, independently, that is, actively obtain knowledge, think and practically act? Experience shows that this task is successfully can be performed, for example, as part of extracurricular activities during summer practice. Creative practice-oriented course in English "The World of Inventions" ("World of Inventions") was implemented with students of the 8th grade of the fourth training course of the St. Petersburg Suvorov

Military School during the period summer practice. Creative practice-oriented course in English “World Inventions” (“World of Inventions”) were implemented with 8th grade fourth grade students. Bachelor's degree at the St. Petersburg Suvorov Military School during the period summer practice. The topic of the training course is directly related to software. Requirements for the content of the subject content of speech by students 8 classes in the socio-cultural sphere. Pupils had the opportunity implement, deepen and expand your knowledge of the English language on the topic, as well as develop the ability to work with a greater understanding of authentic information in Russian - search, selection, compression, abstracting, creation of secondary documents, presentation.

When planning the course, the following tasks were set:

- increasing students' motivation to learn English;
- stimulation of active research interest;
- development of cooperation and critical thinking skills;
- broadening your general horizons;
- development of linguistic, speech, sociocultural competence;
- improving active independent search skills

information on the network and presentation of performance results.

Among the technologies used: communication technology, TRKM, collaborative learning technology, project technology and problem-solving technology training. To date, the school's educational activities (only two year of study, the organizers allocate 160 hours, of which 96 hours in remote mode of conducting webinars and 64 hours in face-to-face shifts) take part students of two age groups: 7–8 grades and 9–10 grades. The category of students is diverse: these are talented children with a high level of development of abilities, providing them, subject to the creation of appropriate educational environment achieving outstanding success in any form activities, and gifted students with a special

predisposition to mastery of a certain educational field (in our case, the educational field of “Philology”), which is characterized by “psychological maturity, which does not mean high IQ, but is associated with a high level of manifestation of social culture" The educational program of the school is designed for two years in the mode of conducting three classes per month in the form of webinars with teachers at the base platform Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment), which is a virtual learning environment. The use of a unified educational information environment (LMS) involves distance learning, organized in virtual classes under the guidance of teacher-curators. Thus, school students have the opportunity to receive weekly consultations from supervising teachers. In addition, twice a year for Students of the Year-Round School undergo face-to-face training sessions – spring and autumn We emphasize that activities in the field of learning foreign languages are one of the humanitarian areas of the Year-Round School. Yes, teachers of the department English language Uzbek State Pedagogical University teach training sessions English language courses for school students.

In accordance with the purpose of the Year-Round School and the assigned tasks, it was a curriculum for two years of study has been developed. The supervising teachers identified the main content vectors of training: sections reflecting the structure of foreign language Olympiad tasks: “Use of English”, “Listening”, “Reading”, “Speaking”, “Writing”. The choice of this direction of educational activity is due to the fact that operational and motivational readiness for successful participation in Olympiads in a foreign language at various stages of their implementation contributes to the implementation of such an important activity principle of the personal development of the gifted child as a principle of creativity Task: find out how and when they appeared, who invented them. The purpose of this lesson was to achieve the following results: 1) personal (formation of skills of cooperation with peers, readiness for self-education); 2) meta-subject (the ability to independently determine the goals of one’s activities, make plans,

monitor and adjust their implementation, own skills of cognitive and educational research activities, the use of different methods of cognition); 3) subject (use of a foreign language as a means of obtaining and presenting information for educational purposes). A system of learning tasks was developed for the lesson, which were aimed at developing relevant competencies. These are 1) quest tasks using a map (after completing the tasks, find and mark objects); 2) text tasks in the form of hints, riddles: students worked with texts, interpreted them. All assignments were written in English. The lesson was conducted as follows. Having received maps indicating the street and the houses located on it, as well as tasks in the form of riddles, hints, questions in English that guided them along the path of searching for “invisible inventions”, the students went to Sadovaya Street, accompanied by the teacher looks for objects to put them on the map. They also decided how to build your search optimally. The quest participants completed the task in pairs or individually - your choice. The teacher monitored the progress of the search, provided advice and monitored compliance with safety rules in public places. In conclusion the walks were summed up results. Next in class, the lesson continued with searching for information about inventions, have become familiar and unnoticeable, but have not ceased to be important.

Thus, the technology used during the excursion lesson contributed to the achievement of the planned results: 1) personal: students deepened their knowledge, but they did not receive ready-made knowledge, the entire process of cognitive activity was built on an independent search for information; 2) meta-subject: students independently planned and adjusted completing tasks while choosing the most effective way to play; independently presented the results of their activities; 3) subject: completing tasks in English, students in practice applied lexical and grammatical knowledge acquired as part of the development school curriculum.

Experience of working with students on projects allows us to highlight the most interesting forms and methods of work, formulate the stages of project preparation, choose forms of control that allow you not only to determine the level achieving substantive results, but also meta-subject ones. There are reasons believe that careful preparation of the project by the teacher is the key to successful children's work. Planning a project should begin by identifying a training topic, fundamental question, problematic and educational issues. Next define its duration, develop evaluation criteria, issue a business card and competently advertise the project so that it inspires students, and they would. We enjoyed working on the topic. Each project has a business card in which all main tasks, expected results, duration are presented project, materials and selected resources, formative assessment techniques. All work on the project can be divided into several stages, at which students develop universal learning actions necessary to solvereal life tasks.

Stage 1. At the first preparatory stage, a starting presentation is offered teachers, during which children determine the topic of their project, roles are chosen and groups are formed. At this stage, regulatory skills develop (the ability to understand the task, take, carry out planning actions and communicative actions (ability to listen and enter into dialogue, cooperate in Group). It is important that the group includes children with different abilities, so the teacher's task is to carefully think through the questions and roles for each group.

Stage 2. Analytical. The stage consists of setting goals, defining tasks, ways to find the right material, maintain your own journals, reports, searching and collecting information, studying material, comparison, analysis and selection the most suitable material according to the topic of the project. Students will need the ability to interpret facts, draw conclusions, and form their own judgments. The role of the teacher at this stage is to teach children to work correctly with sources and

select the necessary material in textbooks, encyclopedias, and the Internet. Reminders and instructions have been developed for this purpose.

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